

PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENTS

IN-PLANE AND THROUGH-THE-THICKNESS

Edwin van Herpt / Maarten Labordus / Edwin Velds / Aldert Verheus
Centre of Lightweight Structures TUD-TNO
e-mail: E.vanHerpt@LR.Tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

Liquid moulding processes like RTM and vacuum infusion are becoming more and more state-of-the-art in the composite industry. Resin flow simulation software for these processes has also been around for many years. One of the key input parameters required for a good flow simulation is the permeability of the fibre reinforcement. No standard, general accepted permeability test has been established yet. Currently, most composite research institutes have developed their own permeability test set-up. Probably, all these set-ups give adequate results for a qualitative flow simulation. A quantitative comparison of the results from one set-up to the results from another set-up has never been performed and will most certainly give very poor correlation.

The Centre of Lightweight Structures TUD-TNO (CLS) has developed a permeability measuring device for accurate in-plane permeability measurements following the conditions for Darcy's Law as close as possible. The permeabilities are tested in the two main flow directions. These directions have to be determined in a separate test. With a point infusion of the reinforcement, an elliptical flowfront can be observed. The main axes of this ellipse correspond to the main flow directions of the reinforcement. The accuracy of the permeameter method is at minimum 1% for one test set-up.

The assumption is correct that a steady state flow method with which the permeability is measured is adequate to model a (non-steady state) filling process. The adequacy is proved by the agreement between the calculation of the propagation of errors and the relative standard deviation (coefficient of variation) of the within-experiment results (both 1%). This paper will describe the experimental set-up and underlying theory. Some results for typical reinforcements will be presented.

Most flow simulation software is still two-dimensional. Therefore, permeability data was only required in two principal directions. Recently, also three-dimensional flow simulation software is developed. But also with two-dimensional flow simulation software, it is possible to investigate local three-dimensional flow phenomena by doing simulations in cross-sections of the laminate. For these three-dimensional simulations, permeability data is required in the third direction: through-thickness. A similar approach as for the in-plane permeability test set-up can be used for a through-the-thickness test set-up.

The overall conclusion is that with the test set-ups described in this paper, it is possible to generate accurate permeability data. This data can be used as input in resin flow simulation software which is needed during the development of the liquid moulding production processes of composite parts.

KEYWORDS

Permeability; flow simulation; Darcy's Law; permeameter; viscous flow

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. VISCOUS FLOW THROUGH POROUS MEDIA

The filling stage of the resin transfer moulding process is considered to be an analogy of ground water flow through soil. A mathematical relation to describe this process, the (viscous) flow through porous media, was formulated by Darcy in 1856. Darcy's law is now generally applied to model RTM. Applied to a one-dimensional flow Darcy's law is:

$$Q(t) = \frac{k(x)A(x)}{\eta(t)} \frac{dp(x,t)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

with

- Q(t): the time-dependent volumetric flow rate (m³/s)
η(t): the time-dependent fluid viscosity (Pa.s)
A(x): the surface area of the cross section of the mould (ml);
A(x) can depend on the position x in the mould
dp(x,t)/dx: the pressure gradient in the flowing resin (Pa/m)
k(x): the apparent reinforcement permeability (m²), characterising
the ease of flow through a reinforcement material

During mould filling, when a resin is injected with a constant pressure in an isotropic reinforcement, the flow direction is constant; the flow velocity decreases in time. In a steady state fluid flow, the flow rate is constant with respect to the magnitude and direction. In a rectangular mould cavity (A(x)=A) containing a reinforcement material with a permeability independent from x, the pressure gradient dp(x,t)/dx equals the linear pressure drop Δp/Δx. With a model viscous fluid, the viscosity is η(t)=η. Then Darcy's law becomes:

$$Q = \frac{kA}{\eta} \frac{\Delta p}{\Delta x} \quad (2)$$

Based on this equation a method is developed to determine the permeability of reinforcement materials, under the assumption that:

- a steady state flow method is adequate to model a (non-steady state) filling process, thus neglecting interfacial phenomena (e.g. fibre wetting, impregnation);
- the reinforcements are isotropic, or, in case of woven (orthotropic) fabrics, the reinforcements are characterised in the principal directions.

Based on equation (2) an apparatus is developed in which the permeability of a (preformed) reinforcement material is measured in a steady state flow of a model fluid instead of a (curing) resin. The cavity of this apparatus contains an adjustable top side so the cavity can be adjusted to the thickness h of the preform. With a constant width b, the surface area of the cross section of the mould A is:

$$A = b h \quad (3)$$

Also, the permeability of a non-preformed reinforcement can be determined as a function of the fibre volume fraction by repeatedly varying the cavity thickness h, thus compressing the reinforcement, and measuring the permeability. The fibre volume fraction V_f is calculated with:

$$V_f = \frac{M_f}{\rho_f h b l_f} \quad (4)$$

with

- M_f : the weight of the (preformed) reinforcement (kg)
 ρ_f : the density of the reinforcement material (kg/m³)
 l_f : the length of the reinforcement sample (m)

The volumetric flow rate Q of the model fluid is determined by measuring the mass of the fluid flow through the mould during a given time interval divided by the density of the model viscous fluid:

$$Q = \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta t \rho} \quad (5)$$

with

- $\Delta m / \Delta t$: the mass of the fluid flown through the mould during the time interval Δt (kg/s)
 ρ : the density of the model viscous fluid (kg/m³)

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The experimental set-up consists of the CLS permeameter, a plastic fluid container, an electronic scale and a personal computer with a data-acquisition system (see figure 1, 2 and 3). It is placed in a laboratory with a temperature control ($22 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$)

Figure 1. Photo of experimental set-up

Figure 2: Experimental set-up (schematic)

CLS permeameter

The CLS permeameter is composed of two U-shaped aluminium profiles with the mould cavity between them, see figure 3. The width and the length of the cavity faces are 125 mm and 520 mm, respectively. Around the perimeter the cavity is closed with glass and aluminium plates clamped to the profiles with toggle clamps. The height of the cavity is accurately adjusted with four screw spindles connected with a timing belt. The height of the cavity is measured with two dial indicators. The upper aluminium profile is dismantled from the mould by a lifting system thus facilitating the placement of the reinforcement in the cavity. In the bottom profile the fluid inlet and outlet are mounted. Furthermore, in the bottom profile three pressure transducers are mounted with a 200 mm spacing.

Height indicator

The dials indicating the mould cavity height are of Mitutoyo, Japan, type 2052F-10 (range 0.01-30.00 mm). The dials are adjusted with steel plates with a known thickness. The plates are placed in the permeameter. After placing the upper mould part on the plates the dials are adjusted to the correct value.

Pressure transducer

The transducer is flush membrane pressure transducer, type GS Sensors XPM10 (operating pressure range 2 bar, sensitivity 100mV)

Fluid container

During an experiment, a fluid is injected from a plastic container which can be pressurised up to 1 bar. However, the applied pressure is typically 0.4 bar, which can be kept constant within 2 mbar with a pressure regulator of Wilkerson, Englewood, U.S.A., type P15-02-000A-K92 (outlet range 0-1 bar)

Figure 3. The permeameter

Electronic scale

The amount of fluid flow through the permeameter is weighed with an electronic scale of Sartorius A.G., Goettingen, Germany, type L420S (range 424 g, readability 0.001 g).

Personal computer and data-acquisition system

The Sartorius scale and the pressure transducers are connected via a 12 bits data acquisition card from Keithley (DAS-1700-1STDA) to a personal computer (Pentium III, 450 Mhz.).

Model fluid

A mixture of glycerol and water is used as a viscous model fluid in stead of a thermoset resin. The viscosity, adjusted with water to a value of approximately 0.1 Pa.s or 0.05 Pa.s for the preforms with very low permeability's, is measured with a rotating cylinder viscometer of Mettler-Toledo B.V. Tiel, Holland, type RM180 Rheomat (system 22 (0.1 Pa.s) or system 11 (0.05 Pa.s), shear rate 200 s^{-1} , accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$ of input set value). The viscometer is adjusted using two viscosimetrical references of 48.32 and 101.5 mPa.s (at 23°C) The density ρ (g/ml) of the fluid is determined by weighing an amount of 250.0 ml fluid in an analytical flask (m_{fl} (g)), the weight of the flask being m_{flask} (g):

$$\rho = \frac{m_{fl} - m_{flask}}{250.0} \quad (7)$$

3. PREFORM PREPARATION

3.1. MATERIALS

The materials that have been chosen for permeability measurements are listed in table 1. All materials contain an amount of meltable binder to enable preforming

Table 1: Materials

Material	Supplier	Type of material	Weight (g/m ²)
Unifilo 750	Vetrotex	Continuous glass mat	450
Injectex EF630	Brochier	Glass fabric (5HS) with open channels	630
G947/E3911	Brochier	Carbon UD 3k	170
E3836	Brochier	Carbon UD 6k	170
G904	Brochier	Carbon fabric (plain)	183
E3833	Brochier	Carbon fabric (plain)	306
Injectex E3795	Brochier	Carbon fabric (5HS) with open channels	306
NCF 6K T700 600	Saertex	Carbon non crimp fabric, biaxial	640
NCF 12K T700 600	Saertex	Carbon non crimp fabric, unidirectional	640

3.2. PREFORMING

The layers of the reinforcement materials are roughly cut from the role (0.6 m x 0.2 m) in the 0°, 90° or ±45° direction and then stacked in the right order, following table 2. In this table, the direction of cutting of the layers is listed; (0)₁₀ indicates that 10 layers, cut lengthwise from the fabric (0° direction), are stacked, (+45/-45)₆ indicates an alternating lay-up of 12 layers at angles of +45° and –45° with respect to the length of the fabric. The lay-ups are preformed, i.e. compressed to the required thickness and heated up to 160°C in an oven. Then, the preforms are cut (sawn) to the right dimensions (length l 490 ±10 mm; width b 125±0.5 mm) with a template of accurate width. Unfortunately, not all the lay-ups could be compressed to the fibre volume fractions aimed for and some lay-ups were compressed more than expected, so there are some deviations between fibre volume fractions aimed for and achieved. The preforming procedure itself worked very well in producing preforms that fit accurately in the mould cavity without short-cut flows.

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

4.1. PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT

The preformed reinforcement is placed in the permeameter cavity. The cavity height is adjusted to the desired level, in order to obtain the correct fibre volume content in the preform. The container with the glycerol-water mixture is pressurised to a pressure of 0.4 bar. After opening the valve at the fluid inlet, the fluid flows through the reinforcement and fills the container on the scale. A custom made LabView data acquisition programme processes the output signal from the scale, the time interval Δt (s) (read from the PC clock) and the output signals from the pressure transducers. The programme automatically determines when the flow has stabilised by analysing the statistical properties of the pressures and mass flow in time. From the data acquired during a period of stable flow, the mass flow Δm/Δt (g/s) and pressure gradient Δp/Δx are calculated with a best-fit method. With equations 2-7, the permeability is calculated:

$$k = \frac{\eta}{bh} \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta t} \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta P} \quad (8)$$

From given values of accuracy and the statistical properties of the stable flow, an estimated error for the permeability is calculated as well. If the operator desires so, the height of the mould cavity can be changed and a new test run is started. After a minimum of two test runs at different fibre volume fractions, the program calculates the constants for the modified Kozeny-Carman equation:

$$\sqrt{\frac{k}{1-V_f}} = c_1 \frac{1-V_f}{V_f} + c_2$$

This equation can be used to estimate the permeability at any desired fibre volume fraction. All results are presented in both tabular and graphical form by the software. After the test is finished, a test report is generated.

5. RESULTS

The results of the permeability measurements are listed in table 1. In the third column the direction of cutting from the fabric is listed; (0)₁₀ indicates that 10 layers, cut lengthwise from the fabric (0° direction), are stacked. (+45/-45)₆ Indicates an alternating lay-up of 12 layers at angles of +45° and –45° with respect to the length of the fabric.

Table 1: Test data

#	Material	Lay-up	Vf	Vf	Permeability (m2)	Standard deviation (m2)
			target	achieved		
1	Unifilo 750	--	30	29	6.9 10-10	3 10-12
2	Injextex EF630	(0) ₁₀	40	42	2.3 10-10	7 10-13
3	Injextex EF630	(0) ₁₂	45	50	6.2 10-11	3 10-13
4	Injextex EF630	(0) ₁₃	50	54	3.2 10-11	1 10-13
5	Injextex EF630	(0) ₁₃	50	54	1.5 10-10	2 10-12
6	Injextex EF630	(+45/-45) ₆	50	50	1.9 10-10	4 10-13
7	Injextex EF630	(0) ₆ (+45/-45) ₃	50	50	1.2 10-10	3 10-13
8	Injextex EF630	((0) ₂ (+45/-45) ₂) ₂	50	50	1.4 10-10	4 10-13
9	Injextex EF630	((0) ₄ (+45/-45) ₂) ₂	50	50	1.0 10-10	6 10-13
10	G947 E3910	(0) ₂₅	50	60	2.1 10-11	2 10-13
11	G947 E3911	(0) ₂₈	55	65	6.5 10-12	2 10-13
12	G947 E3912	(0) ₃₁	60	56	2.6 10-11	2 10-13
13	G947 E3913	(+45/-45) ₁₄	55	61	2.0 10-11	2 10-13
14	E3836	(0) ₂₈	55	61	1.3 10-11	1 10-13
15	E3836	(+45/-45) ₁₄	55	53	9.7 10-11	2 10-12
16	G904	(0) ₁₃	50	44	1.1 10-10	2 10-12
17	G904	(0) ₁₄	55	47	7.6 10-11	2 10-12
18	G904	(0) ₁₅	60	42	1.5 10-10	2 10-13
19	G904	(+45) ₁₄	55	42	9.7 10-11	2 10-12
20	G904	(0) ₇ (+45) ₇	55	50	5.0 10-10	2 10-12
21	G904	(+45) ₇ (0) ₇ (+45) ₇	55	43	4.4 10-10	2 10-12
22	G904	(0) ₇ (+45) ₇ (0) ₇	55	48	4.9 10-11	5 10-13
23	E3833	(0) ₁₃	50	55	5.6 10-11	1 10-12
24	E3833	(0) ₁₄	55	59	7.7 10-12	6 10-13
25	E3833	(0) ₁₅	60	61	1.9 10-11	5 10-13
26	E3833	(+45) ₁₄	55	59	4.7 10-12	1 10-13
27	E3833	(0) ₇ (+45) ₇	55	59	6.3 10-12	3 10-13
28	E3833	(+45) ₇ (0) ₇ (+45) ₇	55	55	3.6 10-11	8 10-13
29	E3833	(0) ₇ (+45) ₇ (0) ₇	55	55	1.3 10-11	2 10-13
30	Injextex E3795	(0) ₁₃	50	55	9.7 10-11	5 10-13
31	Injextex E3795	(0) ₁₄	55	55	1.1 10-10	2 10-12
32	Injextex E3795	(0) ₁₅	60	56	1.3 10-10	7 10-13
33	Injextex E3795	(+45) ₁₄	55	55	4.8 10-11	1 10-12
34	Injextex E3795	(0) ₇ (+45) ₇	55	55	3.8 10-11	8 10-13

35	Injextex E3795	(+45) ₇ (0) ₇ (+45) ₇	55	52	9.1 10 ⁻¹¹	1 10 ⁻¹²
36	Injextex E3795	(0) ₇ (+45) ₇ (0) ₇	55	54	7.1 10 ⁻¹¹	7 10 ⁻¹³
37	Injextex EF630	(90) ₁₂	45	50	2.6 10 ⁻¹⁰	2 10 ⁻¹²
38	Injextex EF630	(90) ₁₀	40	41	5.7 10 ⁻¹⁰	1 10 ⁻¹¹
39	6K T700 600	(0) ₅	60	60	1.8 10 ⁻¹¹	3 10 ⁻¹³
40	6K T700 600	(+45) ₅	60	60	1.8 10 ⁻¹¹	2 10 ⁻¹³
41	12K T700 603	(0) ₅	60	60	4.8 10 ⁻¹¹	3 10 ⁻¹³
42	12K T700 603	(90) ₅	60	60	2.1 10 ⁻¹¹	4 10 ⁻¹³

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. VARIATION OF THE PERMEAMETER METHOD

If the variation in every variable of equation 8 is known, then an approximate mathematical rule can be used to estimate the relative variation in the final result k [reference 2]:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma(k)}{k}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma(\eta)}{\eta}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma(b)}{b}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma(h)}{h}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma(\Delta m / \Delta t)}{\Delta m / \Delta t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma(\rho)}{\rho}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma(\Delta p / \Delta x)}{\Delta p / \Delta x}\right)^2 \quad (9)$$

The relative variance of each component in equation 8 is calculated with the specifications given by the manufacturers of the electronic scale and the viscosimeter, manufacturing tolerances and estimated from the measurements. For a typical test, the relative standard deviation $\sigma(k)/k$ of the permeability k is approximately:

$$\frac{\sigma(k)}{k} \approx \sqrt{(5 \cdot 10^{-3})^2 + (10^{-3})^2 + (2 \cdot 10^{-3})^2 + (5 \cdot 10^{-5})^2 + (10^{-2})^2 + (10^{-3})^2} = 1.14 \cdot 10^{-2} \approx 1\%$$

6.2. PRECISION OF THE METHOD

In general measurements are not exactly reproducible due to random variations. The following definitions are applied to discriminate between different types of variation, thus describing the precision of the permeameter method:

Reproducibility

The variation between measurements on identical materials under different circumstances (different laboratories, equipment (same method, however), operators and laboratory conditions).

Repeatability

The variation between measurements on identical materials under equal circumstances (the same laboratory, equipment, operator and laboratory conditions)

Within-laboratory reproducibility

The variation between measurement on identical materials under different circumstances (equipment, operator and laboratory conditions) but within the same laboratory.

The standard deviations of the average permeability measured within one experiment are listed in table 1. As can be shown by a graph of the standard deviations versus the average permeability, the standard deviation is dependent on the magnitude of the average permeability. The relative standard deviation

RSD_{we} (or coefficient of variation, i.e. the quotient of standard deviation and average permeability) of the within-experiment results however, is roughly constant and equals 1%. This value is in accordance with the calculation of the propagation of errors.

It is difficult to validate the above-defined reproducibility of the permeameter method in this project. To collect data on the reproducibility more laboratories should execute measurements using equipment similar to the CLC permeameter and a similar experimental procedure. Unfortunately, such interlaboratory experiments and the development of calibration materials were not incorporated in the project. The relative standard deviation RSD_{we} of the within-experiment results (1%) can be considered as a "minimum" measure of the repeatability because all the adjustments are kept constant during one experiment. The agreement with the calculated propagation of errors is good. It can be expected that the variation will increase when, for instance, the mould cavity height is re-adjusted during an experiment. The relative standard deviation RSD_{be} of the between-experiment results (6%) approximately characterises the within-laboratory reproducibility: the material sample was unchanged but the circumstances were different (different dates on which the experiments were carried out). Three important but up to now unknown factors are the variations between the fabric samples of one role, the variations between those of several roles, and the influence of the preforming stage on the variation of the measured permeability. The insight in the variation in the permeability results will be increased by measuring several "identical" preforms consisting of an equal amount of fabric layers in a equal height. The conclusion is that the precision of the CLS permeameter method is at minimum 1% during an experiment. The precision decreases to at least 6% by repeating measurements on the same preform. If several identical preforms are measured, the precision will probably further decrease due to unknown variations in the fabrics and the unknown influence of the preforming stage.

6.3. PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENTS

Once a preform has been cut to the right dimensions, the execution of an experiment to measure its permeability is a simple and fast routine. The permeameter turns out to be an adequate apparatus for measuring permeabilities of reinforcement materials. Most materials, according to table 1, are characterised by measuring just a few discrete points (fibre volume fractions). The unique flexibility of the CLS permeameter could be used to measure the permeability of a lay-up over a wide range of fibre volume fractions. If this were to be done, curve-fitting the data with the modified Kozeny-Carman equation will characterise a reinforcement material by only two coefficients. Then, by interpolation the permeability at any fibre volume fraction can be calculated.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The following is concluded:

- By preforming the fabric lay-ups the preparation of the samples is simplified. Special attention should be paid to cutting the preforms to the right dimensions, specifically the width, to avoid runner channels. Also, preforming allows for repeating permeability measurements on the same samples.
- Not all fabrics are suitable to obtain the chosen fibre volume fractions of 50, 55 and 60%. Some preforms have fibre volume fractions lower than 50% due to the too high thickness of the fabrics.
- The measurement of the permeability of a preformed reinforcement sample in the permeameter is a simple and fast routine. The permeameter has turned out to be an adequate apparatus for measuring permeabilities of reinforcement materials.
- The precision of the permeameter method is at minimum 1% during an experiment. The precision decreases to at least 6% by repeating measurements on the same preform. If the permeability of

several identical preforms of an equal number of layers of the same fabric is measured, the precision will further decrease due to unknown variations in the fabric samples and the unknown influence of the preforming stage.

- The assumption is correct that a steady state flow method with which the permeability is measured is adequate to model a (non-steady state) filling process. The adequacy is proved by the agreement between the calculation of the propagation of errors and the relative standard deviation (coefficient of variation) of the within-experiment results (both 1%)
- It is recommended that, additionally, the permeability of the fabrics should be measured over a wide range of fibre volume fractions using the adjustability of the permeameter. By curve-fitting with the (modified) Kozeny-Carman equation the permeability data are more conclusive and applicable than the discrete data from the measurements of this work.
- With a similar test set-up, the permeability through-the-thickness can be measured, see figure 4. This set-up is currently being tested.

Figure 4: Permeability measurement through-the-thickness

REFERENCES

1. R.S. Parnas et al., "Report on Manufacturing Polymer Composites by Liquid Molding", NISTIR 5373, September 20-22, 1993, N.I.S.T., Gaithersbrug
2. J.C. Miller, J.N. Miller, "Statistics for analytical chemistry", Ellis Horwood Ltd., Chichester, 3rd edition, 1993
3. A.E. Schedegger "The physics of flow through porous media", University of Toronto Press, 1957, p.104-105